

	SUBMIT	RANDOM	fromAccountId	type	ABSOLUTE		
1	3	fromAccountId	1	type	1		4
2	6	fromAccountId	13	type	5		8
3	1	fromAccountId	0	type	0		2
4	7	fromAccountId	7	type	2		5
5	7	fromAccountId	6	type	4		4
6	5	fromAccountId	3	type	4		3
7	2	fromAccountId	1	type	2		1
8	3	fromAccountId	2	type	3		1
9	7	fromAccountId	3	type	4		7
10	2	fromAccountId	4	type	1		3
11	4	fromAccountId	5	type	8		5
12	8	fromAccountId	9	type	13		6
13	6	fromAccountId	8	type	7		3
14	2	fromAccountId	0	type	0		4
15	2	fromAccountId	0	type	0		4
16	9	fromAccountId	12	type	5		7
17	3	fromAccountId	0	type	2		4
18	2	fromAccountId	1	type	4		3
19	3	fromAccountId	1	type	3		2
20	5	fromAccountId	10	type	6		6
21	5	fromAccountId	7	type	5		2
22	7	fromAccountId	3	type	5		6
23	2	fromAccountId	1	type	1		2
24	6	fromAccountId	8	type	6		2
25	8	fromAccountId	10	type	5		5
26	7	fromAccountId	8	type	12		6
27	2	fromAccountId	2	type	1		1
28	3	fromAccountId	3	type	3		0
29	6	fromAccountId	1	type	5		6
30	9	fromAccountId	10	type	9		1
	SUBMIT	HUMAN	fromAccountId	type			
1	5	fromAccountId	5	type	5		0
2	7	fromAccountId	7	type	7		0
3	10	fromAccountId	10	type	10		0
4	13	fromAccountId	13	type	13		0
5	12	fromAccountId	12	type	12		0
6	6	fromAccountId	6	type	6		0
7	9	fromAccountId	9	type	9		0
8	10	fromAccountId	10	type	10		0
9	7	fromAccountId	7	type	7		0
10	12	fromAccountId	12	type	12		0
11	6	fromAccountId	6	type	6		0
12	7	fromAccountId	7	type	7		0
13	8	fromAccountId	8	type	8		0
14	10	fromAccountId	10	type	10		0
15	3	fromAccountId	3	type	3		0
16	4	fromAccountId	4	type	4		0
17	9	fromAccountId	9	type	9		0
18	7	fromAccountId	7	type	7		0
19	11	fromAccountId	11	type	11		0
20	5	fromAccountId	5	type	5		0
21	7	fromAccountId	7	type	7		0
22	6	fromAccountId	6	type	6		0
23	11	fromAccountId	11	type	11		0
24	16	fromAccountId	16	type	16		0
25	10	fromAccountId	10	type	10		0
26	6	fromAccountId	7	type	6		1
27	11	fromAccountId	11	type	11		0
28	11	fromAccountId	11	type	11		0
29	8	fromAccountId	8	type	8		0
30	3	fromAccountId	3	type	3		0
TOTAL SUBMITS		TOTAL		TOTAL		AVERAGE	DEVIATION
random	142	139	126	132,5	-0,06690140845		
human	250	251	250	250,5	0,002		

	TOTAL	RANDOM	amount	fromAccount	toAccount	ABSOLUTE		
1	2	amount	2	fromAccountId	3	toAccountId	2	1
2	1	amount	1	fromAccountId	0	toAccountId	3	3
3	3	amount	10	fromAccountId	15	toAccountId	8	24
4	7	amount	20	fromAccountId	12	toAccountId	13	24
5	6	amount	14	fromAccountId	13	toAccountId	13	22
6	4	amount	10	fromAccountId	5	toAccountId	7	10
7	7	amount	18	fromAccountId	15	toAccountId	11	23
8	3	amount	6	fromAccountId	2	toAccountId	2	5
9	7	amount	9	fromAccountId	11	toAccountId	7	6
10	8	amount	13	fromAccountId	16	toAccountId	9	14
11	2	amount	9	fromAccountId	9	toAccountId	13	25
12	4	amount	5	fromAccountId	6	toAccountId	3	4
13	3	amount	10	fromAccountId	13	toAccountId	13	27
14	5	amount	7	fromAccountId	5	toAccountId	11	8
15	1	amount	3	fromAccountId	3	toAccountId	5	8
16	8	amount	12	fromAccountId	16	toAccountId	12	16
17	3	amount	7	fromAccountId	4	toAccountId	4	6
18	6	amount	6	fromAccountId	14	toAccountId	10	12
19	5	amount	10	fromAccountId	10	toAccountId	6	11
20	3	amount	4	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	6	8
21	4	amount	5	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	3	5
22	4	amount	10	fromAccountId	10	toAccountId	7	15
23	3	amount	5	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	2	7
24	9	amount	10	fromAccountId	16	toAccountId	15	14
25	6	amount	13	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	12	14
26	6	amount	19	fromAccountId	17	toAccountId	22	40
27	4	amount	8	fromAccountId	4	toAccountId	5	5
28	4	amount	13	fromAccountId	11	toAccountId	7	19
29	3	amount	3	fromAccountId	2	toAccountId	3	1
30	7	amount	18	fromAccountId	14	toAccountId	18	29
TOTAL	HUMAN							
1	6	amount	6	fromAccountId	6	toAccountId	6	0
2	5	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	toAccountId	5	0
3	9	amount	9	fromAccountId	9	toAccountId	9	0
4	6	amount	6	fromAccountId	6	toAccountId	6	0
5	12	amount	12	fromAccountId	12	toAccountId	12	0
6	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	7	0
7	5	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	toAccountId	5	0
8	9	amount	9	fromAccountId	9	toAccountId	9	0
9	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	7	0
10	6	amount	6	fromAccountId	6	toAccountId	6	0
11	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	8	toAccountId	8	0
12	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	7	0
13	9	amount	9	fromAccountId	9	toAccountId	9	0
14	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	7	0
15	3	amount	3	fromAccountId	3	toAccountId	3	0
16	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	7	0
17	5	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	toAccountId	5	0
18	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	toAccountId	7	0
19	3	amount	3	fromAccountId	3	toAccountId	3	0
20	5	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	toAccountId	5	0
21	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	8	toAccountId	8	0
22	10	amount	10	fromAccountId	10	toAccountId	10	0
23	5	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	toAccountId	5	0
24	11	amount	11	fromAccountId	11	toAccountId	11	0
25	9	amount	9	fromAccountId	9	toAccountId	9	0
26	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	8	toAccountId	8	0
27	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	8	toAccountId	8	0
28	2	amount	2	fromAccountId	2	toAccountId	2	0
29	12	amount	12	fromAccountId	12	toAccountId	12	0
30	9	amount	9	fromAccountId	9	toAccountId	9	0
TOTAL SUBMITS		TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	AVERAGE	DEVIATION	
random	138	280	274	252	268,6666667	0,9468599034		
human	215	215	215	215	215	0		

	SUBMIT	RANDOM	phone	name	message	email	ABSOLUTE				
	11	phone	38	name	39	message	40	email	38	111	1
	2	phone	7	name	3	message	7	email	4	13	2
	4	phone	10	name	6	message	11	email	13	24	3
	6	phone	21	name	26	message	16	email	19	58	4
	6	phone	15	name	20	message	24	email	22	57	5
	6	phone	22	name	18	message	29	email	22	67	6
	7	phone	22	name	29	message	18	email	28	69	7
	2	phone	6	name	3	message	13	email	8	22	8
	10	phone	40	name	32	message	36	email	21	89	9
	4	phone	8	name	6	message	18	email	10	26	10
	10	phone	31	name	35	message	39	email	24	89	11
	6	phone	15	name	19	message	14	email	16	40	12
	5	phone	13	name	11	message	10	email	11	25	13
	4	phone	13	name	9	message	8	email	17	31	14
	9	phone	34	name	34	message	24	email	28	84	15
	6	phone	18	name	13	message	22	email	19	48	16
	3	phone	9	name	9	message	12	email	12	30	17
	7	phone	27	name	18	message	11	email	16	44	18
	9	phone	28	name	25	message	29	email	34	80	19
	6	phone	15	name	20	message	11	email	13	35	20
	5	phone	12	name	16	message	14	email	10	32	21
	4	phone	10	name	16	message	14	email	18	42	22
	6	phone	17	name	23	message	23	email	10	49	23
	8	phone	18	name	25	message	19	email	23	53	24
	9	phone	15	name	21	message	27	email	27	54	25
	7	phone	19	name	17	message	22	email	20	50	26
	6	phone	19	name	13	message	13	email	15	36	27
	4	phone	9	name	7	message	14	email	11	25	28
	2	phone	8	name	3	message	5	email	8	16	29
	3	phone	8	name	15	message	5	email	14	30	30
	SUBMIT	HUMAN	phone	name	message	email					
	5	phone	5	name	5	message	5	email	5	0	
	9	phone	9	name	9	message	9	email	9	0	
	9	phone	9	name	9	message	9	email	9	0	
	4	phone	4	name	4	message	4	email	4	0	
	6	phone	6	name	6	message	6	email	6	0	
	6	phone	6	name	6	message	6	email	6	0	
	9	phone	9	name	9	message	9	email	9	0	
	12	phone	12	name	12	message	12	email	12	0	
	10	phone	10	name	10	message	11	email	10	1	
	11	phone	11	name	11	message	11	email	11	0	
	17	phone	17	name	17	message	17	email	17	0	
	7	phone	7	name	7	message	7	email	7	0	
	15	phone	15	name	15	message	15	email	15	0	
	6	phone	6	name	6	message	6	email	6	0	
	7	phone	8	name	8	message	8	email	8	4	
	10	phone	10	name	10	message	10	email	10	0	
	8	phone	8	name	8	message	8	email	8	0	
	16	phone	16	name	16	message	16	email	16	0	
	7	phone	8	name	8	message	8	email	8	4	
	9	phone	9	name	9	message	9	email	9	0	
	6	phone	7	name	6	message	7	email	7	3	
	12	phone	12	name	12	message	12	email	12	0	
	5	phone	5	name	5	message	5	email	5	0	
	12	phone	12	name	12	message	12	email	12	0	
	7	phone	7	name	7	message	7	email	7	0	
	12	phone	12	name	12	message	12	email	12	0	
	7	phone	7	name	7	message	7	email	7	0	
	10	phone	10	name	10	message	10	email	10	0	
	12	phone	12	name	12	message	12	email	12	0	
	7	phone	7	name	7	message	7	email	7	0	
TOTAL SUBMITS		TOTAL		TOTAL		TOTAL		TOTAL		AVERAGE	DEVIATION
random	177	527		531		548		531		534.25	2,018361582
human	273	276		275		277		276		276	0,0109890110

RUNS	TOTAL	RANDOM	amount	zipCode	verifyAccount	fromAccount	state	pageDown	street	name	phone	accountNumber	city	ABSOLUTE										
1	3	amount	13	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	9	fromAccountId	2	state	12	page.down	3	street	9	name	9	phoneNumber	6	accountNumber	10	city	9	58
2	4	amount	25	zipCode	18	verifyAccount	24	fromAccountId	12	state	21	page.down	5	street	18	name	32	phoneNumber	19	accountNumber	25	city	21	176
3	4	amount	30	zipCode	17	verifyAccount	19	fromAccountId	30	state	25	page.down	4	street	24	name	22	phoneNumber	23	accountNumber	21	city	32	203
4	5	amount	16	zipCode	15	verifyAccount	17	fromAccountId	10	state	23	page.down	6	street	13	name	16	phoneNumber	27	accountNumber	12	city	17	117
5	4	amount	15	zipCode	14	verifyAccount	11	fromAccountId	2	state	14	page.down	4	street	12	name	15	phoneNumber	5	accountNumber	9	city	16	77
6	3	amount	12	zipCode	8	verifyAccount	12	fromAccountId	11	state	11	page.down	4	street	19	name	14	phoneNumber	22	accountNumber	15	city	13	108
7	4	amount	15	zipCode	18	verifyAccount	12	fromAccountId	6	state	10	page.down	4	street	13	name	12	phoneNumber	9	accountNumber	11	city	11	77
8	6	amount	26	zipCode	22	verifyAccount	33	fromAccountId	18	state	27	page.down	6	street	28	name	29	phoneNumber	23	accountNumber	29	city	20	195
9	3	amount	6	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	15	fromAccountId	5	state	10	page.down	3	street	4	name	11	phoneNumber	14	accountNumber	15	city	8	65
10	5	amount	10	zipCode	13	verifyAccount	13	fromAccountId	9	state	10	page.down	5	street	10	name	6	phoneNumber	13	accountNumber	11	city	13	58
11	5	amount	21	zipCode	17	verifyAccount	22	fromAccountId	10	state	18	page.down	5	street	23	name	12	phoneNumber	13	accountNumber	11	city	14	111
12	3	amount	9	zipCode	13	verifyAccount	16	fromAccountId	9	state	14	page.down	3	street	15	name	13	phoneNumber	10	accountNumber	16	city	16	101
13	2	amount	16	zipCode	14	verifyAccount	16	fromAccountId	18	state	16	page.down	3	street	13	name	17	phoneNumber	18	accountNumber	10	city	13	132
14	6	amount	25	zipCode	25	verifyAccount	36	fromAccountId	33	state	37	page.down	6	street	25	name	25	phoneNumber	38	accountNumber	29	city	31	244
15	4	amount	9	zipCode	12	verifyAccount	15	fromAccountId	18	state	14	page.down	4	street	27	name	21	phoneNumber	18	accountNumber	13	city	20	127
16	2	amount	13	zipCode	9	verifyAccount	16	fromAccountId	8	state	6	page.down	2	street	8	name	11	phoneNumber	6	accountNumber	19	city	17	93
17	6	amount	23	zipCode	18	verifyAccount	24	fromAccountId	22	state	20	page.down	6	street	34	name	27	phoneNumber	26	accountNumber	16	city	29	179
18	4	amount	14	zipCode	13	verifyAccount	22	fromAccountId	7	state	20	page.down	5	street	21	name	18	phoneNumber	17	accountNumber	16	city	17	126
19	5	amount	18	zipCode	19	verifyAccount	17	fromAccountId	8	state	16	page.down	6	street	15	name	15	phoneNumber	27	accountNumber	20	city	17	123
20	4	amount	16	zipCode	22	verifyAccount	20	fromAccountId	22	state	22	page.down	4	street	15	name	17	phoneNumber	24	accountNumber	18	city	24	160
21	4	amount	12	zipCode	16	verifyAccount	11	fromAccountId	10	state	15	page.down	4	street	12	name	18	phoneNumber	11	accountNumber	17	city	11	93
22	5	amount	32	zipCode	24	verifyAccount	19	fromAccountId	22	state	26	page.down	6	street	36	name	24	phoneNumber	30	accountNumber	31	city	27	222
23	6	amount	17	zipCode	28	verifyAccount	19	fromAccountId	12	state	28	page.down	6	street	15	name	27	phoneNumber	23	accountNumber	27	city	19	155
24	3	amount	9	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	11	fromAccountId	6	state	8	page.down	4	street	12	name	9	phoneNumber	5	accountNumber	11	city	8	57
25	2	amount	14	zipCode	5	verifyAccount	8	fromAccountId	4	state	4	page.down	2	street	8	name	8	phoneNumber	8	accountNumber	9	city	8	56
26	6	amount	18	zipCode	13	verifyAccount	15	fromAccountId	13	state	11	page.down	6	street	18	name	28	phoneNumber	15	accountNumber	14	city	16	101
27	4	amount	19	zipCode	20	verifyAccount	15	fromAccountId	17	state	18	page.down	5	street	27	name	15	phoneNumber	13	accountNumber	30	city	24	159
28	5	amount	18	zipCode	17	verifyAccount	26	fromAccountId	12	state	25	page.down	6	street	27	name	23	phoneNumber	25	accountNumber	18	city	23	165
29	5	amount	19	zipCode	20	verifyAccount	24	fromAccountId	29	state	26	page.down	6	street	25	name	20	phoneNumber	14	accountNumber	25	city	26	179
30	3	amount	14	zipCode	13	verifyAccount	15	fromAccountId	6	state	19	page.down	4	street	10	name	10	phoneNumber	12	accountNumber	10	city	15	95
TOTAL	HUMAN	amount	zipCode	verifyAccount	fromAccountId	state	page.down	street	name	phoneNumber	accountNumber	city												
1	12	amount	12	zipCode	12	verifyAccount	12	fromAccountId	12	state	12	page.down	12	street	12	name	12	phoneNumber	12	accountNumber	12	city	12	0
2	3	amount	4	zipCode	4	verifyAccount	4	fromAccountId	3	state	4	page.down	3	street	3	name	4	phoneNumber	4	accountNumber	4	city	3	7
3	13	amount	13	zipCode	13	verifyAccount	13	fromAccountId	13	state	13	page.down	13	street	13	name	13	phoneNumber	13	accountNumber	13	city	13	0
4	11	amount	12	zipCode	12	verifyAccount	12	fromAccountId	12	state	12	page.down	12	street	12	name	12	phoneNumber	12	accountNumber	12	city	12	11
5	7	amount	7	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	7	fromAccountId	7	state	7	page.down	7	street	7	name	7	phoneNumber	7	accountNumber	7	city	7	0
6	12	amount	13	zipCode	12	verifyAccount	12	fromAccountId	12	state	13	page.down	12	street	12	name	13	phoneNumber	13	accountNumber	13	city	13	6
7	9	amount	9	zipCode	9	verifyAccount	9	fromAccountId	9	state	9	page.down	9	street	9	name	9	phoneNumber	9	accountNumber	9	city	10	1
8	5	amount	5	zipCode	5	verifyAccount	5	fromAccountId	5	state	5	page.down	5	street	5	name	5	phoneNumber	5	accountNumber	5	city	5	0
9	7	amount	7	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	7	fromAccountId	7	state	7	page.down	7	street	7	name	7	phoneNumber	7	accountNumber	7	city	7	0
10	7	amount	7	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	7	fromAccountId	7	state	7	page.down	7	street	7	name	7	phoneNumber	7	accountNumber	7	city	7	0
11	8	amount	8	zipCode	8	verifyAccount	8	fromAccountId	8	state	8	page.down	8	street	8	name	8	phoneNumber	8	accountNumber	8	city	8	0
12	9	amount	9	zipCode	9	verifyAccount	9	fromAccountId	9	state	9	page.down	9	street	9	name	9	phoneNumber	9	accountNumber	9	city	9	0
13	6	amount	6	zipCode	6	verifyAccount	6	fromAccountId	6	state	6	page.down	6	street	6	name	6	phoneNumber	6	accountNumber	6	city	6	0
14	8	amount	8	zipCode	8	verifyAccount	8	fromAccountId	8	state	8	page.down	8	street	8	name	8	phoneNumber	8	accountNumber	8	city	8	0
15	2	amount	3	zipCode	3	verifyAccount	3	fromAccountId	2	state	3	page.down	204	street	3	name	3	phoneNumber	3	accountNumber	3	city	3	211
16	8	amount	8	zipCode	8	verifyAccount	8	fromAccountId	8	state	8	page.down	8	street	8	name	8	phoneNumber	8	accountNumber	8	city	8	0
17	9	amount	9	zipCode	9	verifyAccount	9	fromAccountId	9	state	9	page.down	9	street	9	name	9	phoneNumber	9	accountNumber	9	city	9	0
18	6	amount	6	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	7	fromAccountId	6	state	6	page.down	6	street	6	name	6	phoneNumber	6	accountNumber	7	city	6	3
19	8	amount	8	zipCode	8	verifyAccount	8	fromAccountId	8	state	8	page.down	8	street	8	name	8	phoneNumber	8	accountNumber	8	city	8	0
20	14	amount	15	zipCode	15	verifyAccount	15	fromAccountId	15	state	15	page.down	14	street	15	name	15	phoneNumber	15	accountNumber	15	city	15	10
21	7	amount	7	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	7	fromAccountId	7	state	7	page.down	7	street	7	name	7	phoneNumber	7	accountNumber	7	city	7	0
22	9	amount	10	zipCode	9	verifyAccount	9	fromAccountId	9	state	10	page.down	9	street	9	name	9	phoneNumber	9	accountNumber	10	city	9	3
23	11	amount	11	zipCode	11	verifyAccount	11	fromAccountId	11	state	11	page.down	11	street	11	name	11	phoneNumber	11	accountNumber	11	city	11	0
24	7	amount	7	zipCode	7	verifyAccount	7	fromAccountId	7	state	7	page.down	7	street	7	name	7	phoneNumber	7	accountNumber	7	city	7	0
25	9	amount	9	zipCode	9	verifyAccount	9	fromAccountId	9	state	9	page.down	9	street	9	name	9	phoneNumber	9	accountNumber	9	city	9	0
26	10	amount	10	zipCode	10	verifyAccount	10	fromAccountId	10	state	10	page.down	10	street	10	name	10	phoneNumber	10	accountNumber	10	city	10	0
27	5	amount	5	zipCode	5	verifyAccount	5	fromAccountId	5	state	5	page.down	5	street	5	name	5	phoneNumber	5	accountNumber	5	city	5	0
28	9	amount	10	zipCode	10	verifyAccount	10	fromAccountId	9	state	10	page.down	9	street	10	name	9	phoneNumber	10	accountNumber	10	city	10	8
29	10	amount	10	zipCode	10	verifyAccount	10	fromAccountId	10	state	10	page.down	10	street	10	name	10	phoneNumber	10	accountNumber	10	city	10	0
30	10	amount	11	zipCode	11	verifyAccount	11	fromAccountId	11	state	11	page.down	10	street	11	name	11	phoneNumber	10	accountNumber	11	city	11	10
TOTAL SUBMITS	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	AVERAGE	DEVIATION									
random	125	504	464	532	391	526	137	536	524	514	518	535	471	2,768										
human	251	259	258	258	254	259	454	256	257	258	260	258	275,5454545	0										

	TOTAL	RANDOM	amount	fromAccount	downPayment	ABSOLUTE		
1	2	amount	0	fromAccountId	0	downPayment	2	
2	7	amount	9	fromAccountId	14	downPayment	8	
3	1	amount	0	fromAccountId	0	downPayment	0	
4	2	amount	1	fromAccountId	3	downPayment	2	
5	1	amount	2	fromAccountId	1	downPayment	5	
6	6	amount	10	fromAccountId	15	downPayment	9	
7	6	amount	3	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	6	
8	7	amount	8	fromAccountId	9	downPayment	9	
9	6	amount	1	fromAccountId	5	downPayment	3	
10	5	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	downPayment	6	
11	3	amount	4	fromAccountId	0	downPayment	3	
12	3	amount	3	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	1	
13	4	amount	1	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	4	
14	0	amount	0	fromAccountId	0	downPayment	0	
15	6	amount	6	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	7	
16	10	amount	12	fromAccountId	6	downPayment	8	
17	3	amount	5	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	3	
18	6	amount	4	fromAccountId	3	downPayment	2	
19	4	amount	1	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	2	
20	6	amount	3	fromAccountId	3	downPayment	4	
21	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	downPayment	5	
22	5	amount	4	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	4	
23	7	amount	2	fromAccountId	6	downPayment	6	
24	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	15	downPayment	7	
25	7	amount	6	fromAccountId	9	downPayment	9	
26	4	amount	0	fromAccountId	0	downPayment	0	
27	2	amount	3	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	3	
28	7	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	downPayment	6	
29	2	amount	0	fromAccountId	2	downPayment	0	
30	13	amount	11	fromAccountId	8	downPayment	6	
	TOTAL	HUMAN	amount	fromAccount	downPayment			
1	11	amount	11	fromAccountId	11	downPayment	11	
2	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	downPayment	7	
3	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	8	downPayment	8	
4	5	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	downPayment	5	
5	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	downPayment	7	
6	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	8	downPayment	8	
7	12	amount	12	fromAccountId	12	downPayment	12	
8	11	amount	11	fromAccountId	11	downPayment	11	
9	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	downPayment	7	
10	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	downPayment	7	
11	12	amount	12	fromAccountId	12	downPayment	12	
12	9	amount	9	fromAccountId	9	downPayment	9	
13	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	8	downPayment	8	
14	3	amount	4	fromAccountId	4	downPayment	4	
15	6	amount	6	fromAccountId	6	downPayment	6	
16	10	amount	10	fromAccountId	10	downPayment	10	
17	4	amount	4	fromAccountId	4	downPayment	4	
18	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	downPayment	7	
19	4	amount	4	fromAccountId	4	downPayment	4	
20	13	amount	13	fromAccountId	13	downPayment	13	
21	8	amount	8	fromAccountId	8	downPayment	8	
22	5	amount	5	fromAccountId	5	downPayment	5	
23	4	amount	4	fromAccountId	4	downPayment	4	
24	7	amount	7	fromAccountId	7	downPayment	7	
25	10	amount	10	fromAccountId	10	downPayment	10	
26	4	amount	4	fromAccountId	4	downPayment	4	
27	12	amount	12	fromAccountId	12	downPayment	12	
28	4	amount	4	fromAccountId	4	downPayment	4	
29	15	amount	15	fromAccountId	15	downPayment	15	
30	6	amount	6	fromAccountId	6	downPayment	6	
	TOTAL SUBMITS		TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL	AVERAGE	DEVIATION
random	150		124	132	131	129	-0,14	
human	234		235	235	235	235	0	

	widget interaction	
	random	human
openaccount	-0,06690140845	0,002
updateprofile	0,1165413534	0,00583090379
transfer	0,9468599034	0
contact	2,018361582	0,0109890110
billpay	2,768	0
findtrans	-0,2008928571	0,005494505495
requestloan	-0,14	0
AVERAGE	0,7774240819	0,01805408287